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Int. Rice Res. Newslett. 10(5):14-15
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Seeds of anther culture-derived lines are available at IRRI

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The IRRI anther culture section has been working on androgenesis of rice pollen for 5 yr. Anther culture was developed to accelerate the development of homozygous varieties.

Anthers are collected from a rice floret at booting stage. Middle uninucleate to early binucleate pollen grain development is the most suitable stage for plating. Anthers are plated in specific callus-induction medium composed of macronutrients and micronutrients with vitamins, sugars, and growth regulators. Calli that form are transferred to a regeneration medium with the same basic nutrients, but perhaps different amounts and sources. Regenerated plants are transferred to a nutrient solution for root development and are grown in the phytotron. After 4 wk, the plants are planted in soil, where they grow to maturity. The seeds are collected, multiplied, and stored in a cold room.

By late 1984, more than 8,000 plants had been regenerated from anther culture. They included haploids, diploids, and polyploids. More than 4,300 derived lines have been produced from varieties (Table 1) and crosses (Table 2) of upland, lowland, deep water, and cold-tolerant rices, and rice adapted to

Table 1. Anther culture-derived lines from varieties, IRRI, 1985.

Variety	Anther culture-derived lines (no.) with seeds
Mingolo	4
Mingolo (TCP 5) ^a	2
Minehikari	5
Minehikari (TCP 258) ^a	15
Jado	2
Baekgogna	1
Paikantao	3
Suweon 290	12
IR40	1
Moosa tarum	2
Hunan 72	4
Taichung 65	1
Leb Mue Nahng III	1
Taichung Sen Yu 195	1
Nong Back	3
Tainan 5	1
BG 90-2	1
Taipei 309	398
Taipei 309 (TCP 1040-6a) ^a	34
Taipei 177	188
Taipei 177 (TCP 260) ^a	26
Taipei 177 (TCP 301-1) ^a	26
Taipei 177 (TCP 701-1) ^a	1
Fujisaka 5	78
Giza 170	154
KK 11 (SR 3044-78-3)	203
Total	1,167

^aAnthers collected from anther-culture plants of the same variety.

problem soils. Field experiments on the anther culture-derived lines are in progress.

IRRI will supply seeds of anther culture-derived lines for breeding studies and screening for tolerance for environmental stresses. *S*

Table 2. Anther culture-derived lines from crosses, IRRI, 1985.

Cross	Parents	Anther culture-derived lines (no.) with seeds
IR29492	IR4683-54-2/Cul. 854	4
IR29863	Silewah/Taichung 65	1
IR29867	Taipei 309/IR36	1
IR30345	Mingolo/D66	1
IR32014	Taipei 309/IR30	1
IR36356	IR29/IR48	4
IR36366	Suweon 290/IR48	6
IR36460	Mi-48/Pokkali	4
IR36781	IR9752-71-3-2/IR19792-15-2-3-3-3	7
IR36870	IR19226-355-1-1-18/IR520-1-26	1
IR37343	IR48/BG90-2	19
IR37344	IR48/Suweon 290	37
IR37348	BG90-2/Suweon 290	1
IR37349	BG90-2/Taipei 309	37
IR37350	BG90-2/Tatsumi mochi	17
IR37352	Suweon 290/BG90-2	9
IR37355	Taipei 309/IR48	1
IR37356	Taipei 309/BG90-2	2
IR37358	Taipei 309/Tatsumi mochi	46
IR37359	Tatsumi mochi/IR48	3
IR37360	Tatsumi mochi/BG90-2	82
IR37361	Tatsumi mochi/Suweon 290	25
IR38641	New Sabarnati/IR27300-124-2	9
IR38644	Ngakywe/IR4570-124-3-2-2-2	7
IR38646	Pawsanbaykyar/IR4570-124-3-2-2-2	6
IR38650	Rodjolele/IR21841-81-3-3-2	2
IR38656	Sabanet Tavangpyan/New Sabarnati	11
IR40344	Suweon 290/Ceysvoni SML	3
IR42800	IR2298-PLIP-3-19-1-2/Wase Toramochi	1
IR43049	Niaw Sanpah Tawng/IR21848-65-3-2	7
IR44173	Chiang Tsenf Tao Ju/Line 62//Suweon 295-11	45
IR44175	Chiang Tsenf Tao Ju/IR1347//Milyang 54	21
IR45445	Tox 896-R-R-102/Chonab 64-117	14
IR45776	Barkat/Calrose 76	5
IR45788	China 972/Calrose 76	35
IR46012	IR19226-355-1-1-30/New Sabarnati//IR25873-22-5-3	2
IR47373	Rodjolele/IR10781-75-3-2-2	2
IR47704	Moroberekan/Kinandang Patong	9
IR47705	Moroberekan/Palawan	22
	Subtotal	510
Chinese crosses		
#19	FuH/Double haploid 14	33
#24	Fujisaka 5/Double haploid 14	1
#27	Fujisaka 5/Double haploid 95	10
	Subtotal	44
SR 11191	SR 10249-B-5/Baegyangbyeo	14
SR 11426	Fukuhikari/Fukei 126	73
SR 11428	Fukuhikari/Fujihikari	14
SR 11433	Chulweon 32/Fujihikari	365
SR 11436	Remei/Fujihikari	39
SR 11440	Seolagbyeo/Fujihikari	3
SR 11451	RAC 3/Hamaasahi	371
SR 11452	RAC 3/Ishiokamochi	773
SR 11453	RAC 3/Fujihikari	910
SR 11455	Suweon 303/Hamaasahi	16
SR 12192	Milyang 64/Shinsonchapyo	2
SR 12200	Mineyutaka/Somachinpyo	4
SR 12212	Norin 6/Sonampyo	25
SR 12246	54BC-68/Sonampyo (Seonambyeo)	8
	Subtotal	2,617
	Total no. of lines from crosses	3,171